

**National
Coordination Point
Research Data
Management**

Data sovereignty, data governance and digital sovereignty

LCRDM

The National Coordination Point Research Data Management (lcrdm) is a national network of experts on research data management (rdm) in the Netherlands. The lcrdm connects policy and daily practice. Within the lcrdm experts work together to put rdm topics on the agenda that ask for mutual national cooperation.

more information: www.lcrdm.nl

“Open Science principles support the increased sharing of data to promote transparency, accessibility, and replicability. In practice researchers and research support staff encounter challenges in balancing Open Science practices a.o. with the GDPR while also ensuring the responsible reuse of data. The FAIR principles guide this process but pose questions on responsibility and decision-making within the research lifecycle, especially in relation to data sovereignty. To address these issues, a task group, comprising diverse stakeholders, explores the interplay of data sovereignty, data governance, and digital sovereignty. Recognizing the operational challenges in policy implementation, the group focuses on practical contributions, developing instruments to aid institutions in navigating data sovereignty issues. The task group emphasizes the need for heightened attention to data governance, sovereignty, and digital autonomy within research institutions. The group aims to elevate awareness through this document, providing tools and recommendations to empower institutions in navigating complexities. The goal is to ensure compliance with regulations while equipping researchers to effectively apply these rules in their daily work.”

**Data sovereignty,
data governance
and digital
sovereignty**

Data sovereignty, data governance and digital sovereignty

How do we know we are in control of our research data?

Introduction and approach

Open Science advocates for the dissemination of as much research data as possible on an open platform to promote scientific progress, enable transparency, and allow for the replication of analyses. It is important to make research results and data accessible in the public domain. However, as such, it is important to share research data but also to maintain control, which can intersect with regulatory issues such as ownership, copyright, privacy, and terms of use (restrictions on informed consent forms, purpose limitations, bans on dual use, prohibitions on resale, etc.).

Open Science can be promoted through the application of the FAIR principles. These principles aim to make research data more findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Open Science and Fair work towards a similar goal but are not equivalent. With the adoption of FAIR, however, some questions arise, such as: Who is responsible for applying these principles, who will be in control of research data that is offered for reuse to other researchers, and who is responsible for making choices about the data if the researcher or even the research group has left the institution? Unfortunately the FAIR principles themselves do not provide answers to these questions.

To better understand the concept of data sovereignty and how it relates to Open Science and FAIR data, the National Coordination Point for Research Data Management (LCRDM) in the Netherlands has established a task group.

The participants of the task group have various backgrounds:

- Data stewards from VU, WUR, UvA
- Researcher from UvA
- Policy advisors from Health-RI, UvA
- Research support from UTwente, UU, SURF and DANS

The list of task group participants is included in v 1.

In this document we not only discuss data sovereignty, but we also discuss data governance, as these are interrelated concepts, as we will show in Chapter 2. Data sovereignty is implicit for the implementation of data governance by research institutions. In addition, the use of (commercial) data infrastructure and services inside and outside of research institutions also requires digital sovereignty. Digital sovereignty can be defined as **a party's right and ability to independently control its own digital data and systems (see Chapter 2 for a more in-depth discussion)**

The task group is convinced that the questions about data sovereignty within the institutions should again be brought to the attention of the people who are responsible for the implementation of data governance. Currently, we see organizations struggling with the misconception that implementing a policy at the institutional level is enough to be able to solve data management issues at the operational level. In practice, questions about responsibility for data remain unanswered or prove difficult to answer because too little time and effort have

been taken to implement the policies. In this task group we recognize the daily struggles with these issues, as expressed in the following illustration:

This task group aims to make a practical contribution to addressing data sovereignty issues in the day-to-day work of research institutions. We have developed instruments to support institutions that produce research data or use research data. The possible implementation of these instruments within institutions is not part of the activities of the task group.

We conclude the document with a short summary and recommendations for implementation within research institutions.

**Definitions of data
governance, data
sovereignty and
digital sovereignty**

Definitions of data governance, data sovereignty and digital sovereignty

Our definitions of data governance, data sovereignty and digital sovereignty

Data governance, data sovereignty, and digital sovereignty are related concepts that intersect. Data governance refers to the organizational structure, oversight and processes involved in the management of data within an organization. Having data governance in place is necessary to ensure data sovereignty. Data sovereignty refers to the level of control and autonomy an organization wields over their data. For example, in the context of data sharing, data sovereignty refers to the autonomy to determine how, when and under which conditions data can be shared. Digital sovereignty can be viewed as a broader concept which also includes control of digital technology and infrastructure. In that sense, digital sovereignty describes an organization's right and ability to autonomously control its digital data and its supporting systems. For academic research, the issue of digital sovereignty is often focused on safeguarding independence from other parties, such as commercial companies for data and research dissemination, storage, data infrastructures and/or software (e.g. academic publishers and big tech).

In the task group we have defined the following topics that play a role in data sovereignty:

- The legal focus (Chapter 3): which laws play a role in determining the rights of parties in the field of data, for example when using data across national borders?
- The control focus: who controls and is responsible for the data, especially when research data is leaving the boundaries of the institution: who regulates access to the data, who can and may determine what happens to the data? And how do you ensure that the data retains a responsible party?
- The financial focus (Chapter 5): who pays for use of the data? Who can make a profit by using the data? Who pays for storage of the data, also when storing data outside of the institution? How does the researcher ensure the ability to retrieve the research data free of costs? Can the researcher benefit from the data, or will the owner of the platform where the data is stored benefit?

Concluding from the definitions above, data governance, data sovereignty and digital sovereignty are related. The three topics overlap where issues of data responsibility transcend the boundaries of the institution, for example when sharing data, storing data on infrastructures of companies, or when collaborating during research with parties outside one's own country and/or the EU.

A large, light green, stylized letter 'B' graphic that occupies the left and center portions of the page. It has a thick, rounded font style with a white cutout in the middle.

**Legal perspective
on data governance
and data
sovereignty**

Legal perspective on data governance and data sovereignty

Legal perspective on data governance and data sovereignty

Data governance can be viewed from a strictly legal standpoint, but policies, guidelines and codes of conduct also play an impacting role. Implementing data governance is important to protect the interests of the institution or researcher, for example when research data is shared.

From the strictly legal perspective, data is a form of information that no one can own; one can only define a responsibility for data. Copyright laws, employment contracts and the GDPR describe a clear responsibility for data on the institutional level. An institution or organization is responsible for all the data that has been produced with the approved participation of their employees or people under the responsibility of the institution, like hired staff. Students bear responsibility for the data that they create themselves, although certain regulations will apply, for instance the Netherlands Code of Conduct for research integrity. In this section we describe the legal conditions on data responsibility within institutions.

3.1 The various laws, policies and codes of conduct that affect data governance

The law defines the hard boundaries of data governance, while internal policies manage the the softer boundaries, as the desired behavior within an organization and further instructions to stay within the applicable regulatory frameworks are elaborated in guidelines at various levels. Data governance is also increasingly impacted by policies on the European level.

Regulatory frameworks affect the governance structure of an organization. At a general level, universities and other institutions of higher education must comply with the Higher Education Act (WHW, Wet op het Hoger Onderwijs en Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek). According to Article 9.4 WHW, a Board of Directors (BoD) (“college van bestuur”) of a university must establish internal regulations for the governance and control of the university in general. The BoD may elaborate further regulations concerning general management, including scientific research at the faculty level (Article 9.5, Articles 9.14.1 and 19.14.3). Compliance with the general regulations is the responsibility of the Dean of the Faculty (Articles 9.12.1 and 9.15.1.b).

The Database Act is another law that impacts data governance. Because of its roots in the European Database regulation, the interpretation of the do’s and don’ts under this legislation is ultimately decided by the case law of the European Court of Justice. Apart from the very generic Database Act and other copyright laws, privacy laws exert the most influence on data governance practice: the GDPR, but also laws addressing medical data (such as the Act on the medical treatment agreement, WGBO), the use of human tissue, the Archive Act, and the Act on the Central Bureau of Statistics, and various other acts concerning the use of government data.

The universities in the Netherlands have jointly agreed to comply with certain

¹ <https://www.nwo.nl/nederlandse-gedragscode-wetenschappelijke-integriteit>

codes of conduct that do not qualify as laws; there are no sanctions if a university acts differently. An example is the 'Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity' (2018).¹ This means that every institution is free to turn these general guidelines into concrete internal procedures, documents and mandates. There are indications that there is a great variety in the ways institutions have adapted the guidelines for their own organization.

² <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/about-parliament/nl/democracy-and-human-rights/fundamental-rights-in-the-eu>

Last but not least, the European Union has developed several policy documents, such as a Digital Agenda for Europa, and regulatory documents such as a Regulation concerning a Framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union (EU/2018/1807)². Also, international sanctions and export control laws (on both a national and European level) impact data governance within organizations. In one way or another, there is, or will be, an increasingly strong influence from 'Brussels' on practical data governance at an institutional level.

3.2 The legal perspective in practice

In many cases, it is unclear what being responsible for data entails in practice. In many institutions, central data policies state that responsibility for the data has been delegated to the research institutions or even the researchers in general, but what this means for individual researchers is not always clear. This becomes clearer, however, when external parties are involved, such as data subjects, data users, or data processors. We must keep in mind that it is not the individual researcher who bears the responsibility (and liability) towards such third parties or even authorities such as the Dutch Data Protection Authority, but instead the institution, for all breaches of contract (including the results of sloppy research) or violations of privacy law.

There appears to be a gap between policymakers and researchers within institutions. At the institutional level, the policies are mainly targeted at reducing risks (for example those arising from the GDPR), while the researcher has many more issues to consider, for example protection of their rights to the data. Also, the researcher does not always have the means nor the information at their disposal to make the right decisions or to be able to take action.

The central data policy of the institution often applies to data collected during the research project. Once a research project has been completed, it is often not clear what the responsibilities should be. As a result, it may happen that within the organization there is ambiguity regarding who is ultimately responsible for making future decisions for the data when there is no known individual or department with this role directly tasked with this responsibility.

The responsibilities of the institution for the data produced by students are not always clear. If a student produces research data while supervised by a researcher of the institution, the research data falls under the responsibility of the institution. But to the individual students and the supervisors, this responsibility is not always understood. We recommend institutions to create and communicate clear rules and procedures for students and their research data.

Funding organizations such as NWO have an interest in addressing data governance issues. For example, they require research data to be archived after a research project has finished, as openly as possible, and with the metadata openly

³ See for example the [DANS Data Stations Policy](https://dans.knaw.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/DANS-Data-Stations-Policy.pdf) on which responsibilities DANS takes on, and which it does not, as a service provider and curator of deposited data: <https://dans.knaw.nl/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/DANS-Data-Stations-Policy.pdf>. Note that the data within a dataset are not changed by a repository.

available. The metadata should specify who is responsible for the data, with a clear access procedure if sharing restrictions are in place. When data is deposited outside the organization, for example with a trustworthy (certified) digital repository, the responsibility for the data remains nonetheless with the depositing organization. In general, an agreement between the depositor and the repository should be put in place, especially when transferring some responsibilities (like curation of datasets) to the repository organization.³

The interpretation of responsibilities related to data also differs between institutions. In practice, this can make it difficult for researchers who collaborate with other institutions to determine the responsibilities in a particular situation. This becomes even more complicated when a partner institution is situated in another country, especially when located outside the EU, where other values and other laws might be applicable. This is very common in academic research. It is therefore always important to establish collaboration agreements specifying data governance, not only during but also after the research project.

Data governance is therefore an important issue within institutions, but also across institutions. This is not just about policies, but also about solving practical questions. Due to the speed of digitalization within education and research, the urgency is only increasing. But before we can answer questions about data governance and data sovereignty, the internal data policies must first be clear within the institutions, and that is not always the case,

Digital sovereignty issues will add to the complexity. For example, according to the GDPR, storing personal data in a non-EU infrastructure is subject to restrictions. However, one problem is that it is not always clear where the data will be stored when using a cloud infrastructure.

The background consists of several overlapping geometric shapes. A large orange shape is on the left, with a light green shape overlapping its top-left corner. Another light green shape is on the right, overlapping the orange shape's right edge. A large orange shape is at the bottom, overlapping the light green shapes. The text is positioned in the bottom-left area, overlapping the light green and orange shapes.

**Practical tools to
increase control
over research data**

Practical tools to increase control over research data

Control over research data deals with several aspects that all can be derived from the questions on data governance, data sovereignty and digital sovereignty:

- Who is responsible/accountable for the data and who will actually deal with the data within your organization?
- Who is responsible for the choices about the data if you want to offer data for reuse outside your institution?
- How can you, and do you need to, stay in control of your data if you store your data outside your organization?

In order to assist institutions in addressing these various issues, the task group has jointly worked on practical tools in the field of data sovereignty and digital sovereignty. This concerns the following tools:

- A RACI for use within an institution. (4.1)
- RDM principles and guidelines for application in practice.(4.2)
- A decision tree for the decisions in three use cases. (4.3)
- Special environments for sharing sensitive data. (4.4)
- Recommendations for digital sovereignty. (4.5)

The tools have been put forward by the members of the task group, based on the issues they encounter in practice with regard to data and digital sovereignty. The task group does not intend to provide a complete set of related tools, but mainly wants to provide tools that other research supporters or administrators within research institutions can use to deal with the challenges in their daily work.

⁴<https://nl.wikipedia.org/wiki/RACI-model>

4.1 RACI

A RACI⁴ is an overview of the parties or individuals who are responsible for the implementation (Responsible), who are ultimately responsible for the execution of the tasks (Accountable), who must be consulted (Consulted), and/or who must be informed (Informed). A separate RACI could be drawn up for each institution, based on the agreements that apply within that institution.

In Appendix 2 we have included an example of an institutional level RACI. This RACI can be used within an institution to make visible who is responsible for what, but also to assess whether all responsibilities have been allocated.

4.2 RDM principles and guidelines for application in practice

Appendix 3 contains a practical example of RDM principles and guidelines with resulting instructions for researchers, which can be used as a template and adapted to specific circumstances, including in other disciplines. The template provides clear handles for data governance, as it describes the processes and responsibilities involved in the management of data.

4.3 Decision trees

Appendix 4 contains decision trees of three use cases around data after the data have been archived, mostly after a research project has been completed. This is based on the actual situation within an institution, but is described more generally, so that it can serve as an example for setting up a process within another institution.

4.4 Special environments

Sharing sensitive data proves challenging. Legal issues make this especially difficult. In the Netherlands, initiatives and pilots try to create solutions for sharing sensitive data. Such initiatives are for example:

- Amsterdam Data Exchange (AMDEX)
- Research Data Exchange (RDX)
- SANE (Secure ANalysis Environment)
- Personal Health Train
- ODISSEI environment

Appendix 5 contains a short description of these initiatives.

4.5 How to increase digital sovereignty

Issues surrounding digital sovereignty are complex and require solutions that take many years to develop. While in many respects the issues need to be addressed at a European and national level, research institutions and even individual researchers can certainly help to increase digital sovereignty and stay away from the long arms of the high tech companies, as demonstrated in the picture below:

⁵ Examples based on Bijsterbosch et al. 2022, Stolwijk et al. 2022; Fig. 6.1

Recommendations in this respect are for example⁵:

- Use infrastructures, services, and technologies with shared values on for example privacy, and always make sure to use appropriate contracts to ensure control over your research data.
- Raise awareness. Research practitioners are often not aware of best practices with regard to digital sovereignty: where should they put research data in the short term and the long term, how can they exchange (sensitive) data and yet retain control over the use of their data? This Open Science Dilemma needs solutions. The first steps for these solutions could be found in projects and pilots that are running at the moment, like Personal Health Train, RDX and AMDEX (see Appendix 5).
- Provide support on a central level. By providing training and information, research support departments can help researchers to make choices for themselves and protect their research data.

**The financial
aspects**

The questions around data governance lead to the question of who bears the costs of storing and archiving data. During the active phase of research projects this is generally very clear for all parties involved. It becomes more complicated after the research project has finished. Data can be stored in external repositories, where in some cases payment is required. Issues can arise when data governance for data stored in external repositories becomes unclear, and payment for archiving services is due. Ultimately, the research data could be lost if payments are blocked. As a task group, we feel the institution is responsible for providing the financial support for long-term storage and/or for long-term storage facilities.

Research data is increasingly archived for longer periods of time (over 10 years). Also, the volume of each data set is increasing. Since the amount of research data is growing exponentially, this will become an issue within the coming years. Our opinion is that institutions need to address the financial aspects of long-term data governance aspects, for instance archiving and reuse. For example, researchers should be encouraged or required to describe both short-term and long-term data governance topics (e.g. data storage costs) in their proposals. An institution should write it into their budget to set up and maintain, or to outsource, storage opportunities, and to provide support to researchers in doing this.

Financial issues can also arise when digital sovereignty issues are not considered in selecting short-term storage facilities for research data. Academic institutions can safeguard their digital sovereignty by working with open source alternatives, cooperate by developing open source alternatives, or use European and/or non-profit/academic support storage and processing facilities.^{6,7} Maintaining open source facilities can be costly as well. When using commercial solutions, good contractual practice can contribute to digital sovereignty, for example an agreed exit strategy. This exit strategy can provide for certainties about the ability to retrieve the data from the external platform without cost.

We recommend adapting contractual practice within institutions to provide for appropriate data exit strategies in legal contracts on storing research data. With regard to long-term storage, next to an institutional data archive suitable for the secure and persistent preservation of all types of research data, a trustworthy repository should be chosen (i.e. where a good contractual agreement is in place; moreover storage of files tends to be normally free or relatively cheap up to a certain size at these types of repositories).

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-governance-act>

⁷ Stolwijk et al. 2022; Bijsterbosch et al. 2022

The background features a large, abstract graphic composed of overlapping organic shapes in two colors: a vibrant orange and a light, lime green. The orange shapes form a large, irregular shape on the left side, with a circular cutout in the lower-left quadrant. The light green shapes fill the remaining space, creating a layered, modern aesthetic.

Conclusions and recommendations

Conclusions and recommendations

As the strategic objective of many institutions is to increase the FAIRness of data, reuse will probably increase in the years to come. The same can be expected of the reuse of research data beyond the boundaries of organizations. The challenge of staying in control of your (sensitive) research data is becoming increasingly important.

This task group feels that data governance, data sovereignty and digital sovereignty need to get more attention in research institutions. In practice, researchers and research support staff struggle daily to deal with questions about who decides about sharing data externally, how to keep control over data after these are shared, and about what infrastructure to use. In any case, institutions are responsible to ensure compliance with rules, regulations, and internal policies in the field of research data, but also to create the conditions in which researchers are able to understand and apply all these rules and policies.

The topics to be dealt with are not simple, certainly not when the issues concern data being transferred from the own institution to organizations outside. This task group wants to contribute to solving this task of the institutions with the publication of this document, with the tools described herein, with the recommendations, and by bringing the document to the attention of the umbrella organizations, the institutions themselves, and within the institutions to research support staff.

With this document we would like:

To increase awareness in the research institutions for:

- The importance of data sovereignty in the data governance. The questions regarding data sovereignty should be brought to the attention of the people who are responsible for the implementation of data governance. Implementing a policy at the institutional level is not sufficient to bring it into practice. It could be considered to incorporate this topic into the proposed building blocks of the data steward job curriculum.
- The importance of digital sovereignty.

To encourage the research institution to implement measures to improve data sovereignty, data governance and digital sovereignty:

- We recommend adapting contractual practice within institutions to guarantee data sovereignty, ensure that agreements are in place with trusted parties where responsibilities are clearly defined. In case external foreign parties are used for storage facilities, ensure appropriate data exit strategies in legal contracts on storing research data when this data is managed by an external organization under foreign laws, both during and after the project.
- Provide support for researchers. Researchers are often not aware of best practices with regard to digital sovereignty: where should they put data in the short term and in the long term, how can they safely exchange data? By providing training and support, research support departments can help.⁸

⁸ Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands, Mijke Jetten, Marjan Grootveld, Annemie Mordant, Mascha Jansen, Margreet Bloemers, Margriet Miedema, & Celia W.G. van Gelder.

We want to support institutions, researchers, and research support staff to give substance to data sovereignty, data governance and digital sovereignty in daily practice by providing the following practical tools:

- A decision tree, in appendix 4 to support the communication to the cooperating parties, so they know who to address.
- A RACI matrix in appendix 2 as a tool to ensure all responsibilities are covered within the organization.
- An example document for a practical implementation for RDM policy and guidelines in different layers of the institution in Appendix 3.

Finally, with this document we want to raise attention to the following aspects:

- The conversation between institutions about the transitions in data sovereignty in the collaboration between institutions or between institutions and commercial parties.
- The possibilities to promote FAIR in case of sensitive data, by making use of special tools (like AMDEX, RDX and/or Sane).
- The advice to research institutions to take responsibility for providing long term archiving solutions for research data, along the lines of the institution's policies on data governance.
- The consideration of organizing support on digital sovereignty on a national level, thus creating a national helpdesk on this topic, as this topic is of great interest to all institutions.

Appendix

Appendix 1. List of data sovereignty task group participants

Name	Position	ORCID
Lucy O' Shea	Data Steward VU	0000-0002-0352-4905
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Sounding Board members

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Christina Elsenga	RUG	0000-0001-5799-282X
Tanya Yankelevich	TU Delft	

Appendix 2. RACI

An RACI is an organizational instrument where the letters stand for:

- Person or organization that makes sure the work is carried out
- Person or organization who does the work or takes decisions during the work in progress
- Anyone or any organization who must be consulted (related to the decision/work)
- Anyone or any organization who must be informed (related to the decision/work)

This can loosely be translated into a data management RACI or R2A2CI, in this case:

- Responsible for (correctly) handling the data (R-hand)
- Responsible for making decisions related to the data (R-dec)
- Accountable legally (A-leg)
- Accountable financially (i.e. who pays) (A-fin)
- Who needs to be involved/Consulted (C)
- Who needs to be Informed? (I)

An RACI can be created on the level of a process. Typically, an RDM RACI for data archiving after a research project has finished could look like this:

RDM RACI for data archiving

	RvB	Faculty board	Research group PI	Researcher	Ethical com.	Data manager
R-hand				X		
R-dec			X			
A-leg		X				
A-fin		X				
C						
I						X

⁹ Research Data Lifecycle by LMA Research Data Management Working Group is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License.

RACIs can be created for any processes within the institution that deal with steps in the data life cycle⁹, as presented in the next figure:

- **PLAN & DESIGN:** Plan processes from onboarding to project closure and data resources
- **COLLECT & CREATE:** Organization and integration of data sets and collection processes
- **ANALYZE & COLLABORATE:** Processing and analyzing data should be collaborative and documented
- **STORE & MANAGE:** Each stage of the Biomedical Data Lifecycle revolves around the management of data storage
- **EVALUATE & ARCHIVE:** Identify essential research records and evaluate for retention
- **SHARE & DISSEMINATE:** Establishing and supporting the reach and impact of your data
- **ACCESS & REUSE:** Ensuring the broad utility of your research data efforts for other researchers

The **legal accountability for all data related issues** always lies with the overseeing legal entity, i.e., the university, university medical centre, or hospital. This legal entity is represented by its Board of Directors or the Dean of a Faculty. Individual employees/researchers are **ONLY** entitled to sign an agreement

concerning data when internal mandate regulations allow them to do so. They then will expressly sign on behalf of the Board or the Dean.

Due to the legal position of the institution, it is liable towards (external) third parties for compliance with laws, regulations, codes, and for any damages or fines due to non-compliance, including breach of terms of agreements concluded with:

- Users of data (insufficient data quality, availability, proper accessibility, etc.)
- Providers of data (breach of terms under which data is/was provided, loss of data)
- Funding agencies and other stakeholders.

The legal entity, being the employer of its staff, is responsible for internal accessibility and usability of data by staff/students to enable these stakeholders to do their work as employees or students. If this is impossible, further liabilities towards third parties may arise because staff are unable to perform as agreed.

Financial accountability regarding collecting, storage, management and processing can be devolved to particular budget holders (faculty, institution, research unit, project, IT services unit, etc.)

Responsibility for handling the data (collecting, storage, making accessible, management) can be devolved to particular (specialized) units within the university or within faculties or institutions.

Responsibility for giving actual access to the data should be delegated to a central or local Data Access Committee, consisting (at least) of scientists, ethical, financial and legal (contracts, privacy) experts. In case of data to which no particular legal regimes such as health or privacy law apply, leaving the decision for granting access (or not) to an individual scientist should at least be properly monitored by 'higher levels' in order to prevent any conflict with institutional policy.

Some additional legal background:

Every collection of data is subject to the principles of Dutch and European database law. In the context of database law, the term database covers any collection of independent works, data or other materials arranged in a systematic or methodical way and individually accessible by electronic or other means.

Each staff member is an employee of the university and bound by a labour contract to the employer. A data collection is the result of a staff member's activities as a paid employee, combined with additional investments made by the employer in setting up and maintaining the technical and management infrastructure in which the data is stored. All finances involved are either obtained from the employer's own funds, or from external funding (grants or other) based on agreements between the employer and the funding partner.

According to Dutch database law, the 'owner' of the database is the party that has made substantial investments in collecting, storing and managing the data. It is the owner, in this case the employer, who is entitled to decide on access and use of the database as such. Copying a database is only allowed with the owner's consent, and the same holds for transferring a database from the owner's premises or technical infrastructure to somewhere else. It is, therefore, not the employee who has any personal entitlement to the database, regardless of decades of blood, sweat and tears that were personally spent to create it and enhance its worldwide reputation.

Appendix 3. Research data management principles and guidelines: A blueprint for research data management, with an accompanying set of instructions for researchers

¹ The text of this appendix is based on a policy document from the Faculty of Social and Behavioural Sciences of the University of Amsterdam (contact address: f.j.oort@uva.nl). The policy principles were originally drafted to apply to the management of the types of research data commonly used in the social sciences, humanities and medicine. Wider application of these principles to other disciplines, possibly with adaptation, seems possible.

² Wilkinson, M. D., et al. (2016). Comment: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, [160018]. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

The LCRDM Data Sovereignty Task Group promotes responsible Research Data Management (RDM) and suggests principles and guidelines that universities might want to adopt. ¹

Data should be FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.² However, data sharing is subject to conditions imposed by laws and regulations (such as the General Data Protection Regulation; GDPR), as well as data sovereignty considerations that we must take into account to protect the interests of the universities and its researchers. We therefore distinguish between FAIR archiving (closed) and FAIR publishing (open). All data should be *archived* with full provenance in a closed archive (FAIR for the institute) and a selection of data suitable for publication should be *published* on an open platform (FAIR for the outside world).

The following describes the principles for archiving and publication, its limitations, the three types of storage required (Figure 1), the administrative and scientific quality control required, and the different RDM stages with corresponding instructions.

1. Policy principles

There are two guiding principles that underpin RDM policy: The archiving principle and the publication principle.

The archiving principle: We strive to store all data in a closed archive, indefinitely, with full provenance description, FAIR for the institute only.

Full provenance consists of (1) documentation of where the data came from, how they were collected, by whom, for what reason, who was involved, and what methods and instruments were used and (2) a description of the steps taken to get from the original raw data to the processed data and the results. The archive must be closed because the raw data and provenance description usually contain confidential information.

Justification of the archiving principle:

- **Duty of care:** Although ownership of research data is ill-defined (and controversial), the institution must have access to all data collected under its responsibility, as it is responsible for ensuring compliance with relevant laws and regulations governing the use and handling of the data.
- **Secure storage:** A secure and closed archive managed by the university ensures that data is protected from loss, unauthorised access, and inappropriate use over the long term. This is particularly important for data that is privacy sensitive or should not be released for other reasons (e.g., intellectual property, prevention of dual use, resale).
- **Safety in the practice of working with data:** Once the raw and potentially sensitive data has been properly archived, it is possible to de-identify the data and work with pseudonymised data instead. This allows sensitive data to be removed from workspace storage.

- **Prevention of data loss:** Should a researcher accidentally lose data or make irreversible changes; it is still possible to retrieve previous versions from the archive.
- **Transparency:** Archiving data with full provenance allows verification of data, processing, and analysis steps, etc., when appropriate, which can also have a positive feed-forward effect that encourages good data practices.
- **Reusability:** If researchers want to continue working with the data at a later stage or in a new study, archiving it with full provenance makes it possible to retrieve and reuse the data. This allows for follow-up research with other analysis techniques or new research questions, and more.

The principle is that all data should be retained indefinitely, but there are of course limitations on the extent to which this is possible and considerations to be taken into account, such as:

³ In accordance with Article 89(1) (GDPR)

- **Purpose limitations:** Personal data should only be archived for specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes and not be processed further in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes.³
- **Privacy:** Under the GDPR, personal data can be archived for varying lengths of time, provided there is a clearly enforceable policy in place, the data is not archived for longer than necessary for the defined purposes, and participants have been informed. This in turn means that data that include personal data cannot be archived indefinitely, and its limitations are already defined within the informed consent letters, and privacy agreement.
- **Contractual agreements:** Archiving may be restricted by agreements with other parties regarding retention periods.
- **Information duty:** A researcher should not archive research data without informing participants that their personal data will be archived. An informed consent should provide for this.
- **Policies and guidelines:** Institutions from various research disciplines have their own guidelines on Research Data Management (RDM) and subsequent archiving practices. The rationale behind the retention period for personal data must be clearly defined to justify the retention period when an authority requests such information.
- **Cost-benefit consideration:** Archiving large amounts of data for an indefinite period can be very costly. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully consider the costs of archiving in relation to the benefits it provides.

The publication principle: We strive to publish as much data as possible, accessible via a publication platform, as early as possible, with full description of terms of use, FAIR for the world.

Early and extensive data sharing promotes transparency and is in line with the principles of open science, which aims to promote the progress of science by enabling (interdisciplinary) collaboration, re-use, aggregation, meta-analysis, etc., and to avoid unnecessary duplication of research. Moreover, most research is publicly funded, and research data are considered a public good, so there may even be an obligation to make research data publicly available.

However, the extent to which data can be shared unconditionally may be limited by legal and sovereignty issues. The considerations outlined for the archiving principle also apply to the publication principle. There are also additional considerations that need to be taken into account:

- **Copyright issues:** According to legal scholars, there is no ownership, intellectual property, or authorship of research data, so copyright cannot be regulated.
- **Privacy:** Data with personal information cannot be shared due to privacy requirements (GDPR), informed consent restrictions, and possible purpose restrictions.
- **Conflicting regulations:** Institutional, national, and international regulations and directives may conflict (e.g., GDPR, Digital Services Act, Digital Markets Act, Data Governance Act, EU Directive on Open Data and the Re-Use of Public Sector Information, Text and Data Mining articles in the EU Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market).
- **Information duty:** A researcher may not share research data without informing participants that their personal data will be shared. Informed consent should provide for this.
- **Contractual agreements:** Publication may be prevented by agreements with other parties on embargo periods, retention periods, purpose limitations, dual use prohibitions, resale prohibitions.
- **Knowledge safety:** Researchers and institutions must consider the possibility of data being misused by other parties, particularly for dual-use applications (i.e., those that can be used for both civilian and military purposes).
- **Digital sovereignty:** The university holds the research data and should protect itself from commercial lock-in by preventing commercial services from harvesting its data and becoming dependent on commercial endeavours, thereby compromising its independence and scientific integrity and its public service mission.

2. Prerequisites

To work according to the principles mentioned above, researchers require specific infrastructure. This includes appropriate storage facilities and support for archiving and publishing research data. Additionally, to safeguard data sovereignty, access to research data must be regulated.

The data holder should decide which data to share, with whom, and under which conditions. Data descriptions can be published on a publication platform, with a link to a contract with terms of use. Only if an interested user agrees to the terms of use will he or she get access to the data. The user can then either download the data or perform remote analysis on the data, getting the results but not the data itself. The University of Amsterdam and SURF are developing a Research Data Exchange (RDX) that regulates such access, including the automated recording of signed usage contracts, for auditing purposes.⁴

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8269272>

Three types of storage

Three types of storage are required to enable researchers to comply with the archiving and publication principles (see Figure 1):

- Workspace storage is temporary (e.g., cloud storage, local storage, laptops, or desktops) and is used in the collection, processing, and analysis of data for the duration of a research project. This storage is only accessible to researchers. The use of unapproved, non-EU cloud service storage is not permitted (digital sovereignty).
- Secure, closed storage for long-term archiving of data packages. Data packages include full provenance descriptions and appropriate metadata for indexing and

⁵ Digital sovereignty describes a party's right and ability to independently control its own digital data and systems. It includes control over all digital tools and services that are used in research, including data, software, hardware, and other digital assets.

Figure 1: Workspace storage, archiving, and publication of data in separate locations.

cataloguing purposes. The archive is a closed facility, inaccessible to researchers themselves, but the archived data must be FAIR for the institute so that access can still be granted if required. Data packages can only be retrieved with the permission of the faculty dean or institute director.

- Open access publication platforms for the publication of data descriptions. Data packages that are suitable for publication (i.e., do not contain sensitive data) should be deposited in a repository for an indefinite period of time and referenced on a publication platform (e.g. DANS, OSF, ODISSEI, Zenodo). Access to these data packages should be regulated by an RDX (Research Data Exchange), subject to terms of use.

During the research project, upon completion of (substantial parts of) data collection or processing, the researcher should compile a data package and submit it to the data steward for archiving. Such a data package includes the original raw data, any processed data, and a full description of the origin and processing. As data packages for archiving contain confidential information, all storage for archiving is closed, accessible only to a limited number of people, only after permission from the director or dean. Data suitable for publication are packaged together with a data description and a contract with terms of use in a 'publication package' and submitted to the data steward for review and archiving prior to publication.

Administrative and scientific quality control

Universities are responsible for good research data management (RDM) and the necessary IT infrastructure, in compliance with legal and institutional policies. For this reason, it is not possible for researchers to archive their data themselves, without the intervention of the data steward. And for researchers to self-publish their data should also be discouraged.

Data stewards should act as gatekeepers in the (closed) archiving and (regulated) publication of data. They must check, or have checked, that data packages comply

with laws and regulations, institutional policies, informed consent and contractual agreements, the FAIR principles, the Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, that provenance descriptions are complete, that metadata are correct and complete, that terms of use are correct and complete, and that any licenses have been applied correctly. If data packages are not yet compliant, the data stewards can also assist researchers by helping them, or arranging for someone else to help them, to make them compliant.

Data stewards may not have the time or expertise to check all data packages for all of the above. To support data stewards, a reference system should be in place to easily access legal assistance help for checking legal points, ethics committee members for checking informed consent, data scientists or experts with specific knowledge within the research institutes for checking data provenance and adherence to FAIR principles, and librarians for checking metadata and maintaining a catalogue of archived and published data. Additionally, the assessment of standard cases should be automated as much as possible.

3. RDM stages and instructions for researchers

Good research data management is important throughout the research cycle. We distinguish six stages of RDM (described in a particular order, although they do not always have to be carried out in that order).

Stage 1: Study Preparation

Core Questions

- Are there services in place for researchers to register new research projects including all required procedures, such as an Ethics Review, Informed Consent, Data Management Plan, Privacy Agreement, Pre-registration?
- Do these services offer insights and solutions related to data sovereignty, including legal compliance, data control and responsibility, and financial considerations?
- Is there staff available to support researchers during this process, such as an Ethics Review Board, Data Stewards, Security Officers, etc.?

Steps

1. The researcher reports a new research project via the appropriate channels⁶ provided by the university.
2. The researcher writes a data management plan (DMP) by answering a list of questions and uploading relevant documents.
 - a. Note that a DMP may also include data protection questions.
 - b. If, based on the data protection questions in the DMP (or another form), there appears to be major privacy risks for research participants, the researcher is referred (by the data steward) to a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA).
3. The DMP includes questions that provide insight into the tools and services that are being used (digital sovereignty).
4. The DMP includes questions related to data exchange(s) with third parties. If there appears to be a cooperation with third parties, the researcher should be directed to the data steward or the privacy team, which is able to decide if a data processing agreement (DPA) is required and which type of DPA.
5. Once the DMP is approved (by the data steward), the appropriate channels will record the DMP.

⁶ For example, the UvA established a management service for registering research projects including all required research preparation procedures, such as an Ethics Review and Data Management Plan.

6. For research involving the collection of data from human subjects (either directly or obtained from third parties), and where the research meets the criteria for review by the relevant ethics committee, the researcher applies by answering a list of questions and uploading relevant documents within the project registration service.
 - a. In case the research project is subject to the “Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act” (*Wet Medisch-Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek; WMO*), the researcher will be referred to the Medical Ethics Committee (METC).
 - b. If the project involves cooperation with other Dutch universities and has been approved by an ethics committee of another university, the project does not need to be approved again. Ethics committees accept approval from other Dutch universities. (Note that this is not the case for all universities, some have other policies in place.)
7. When the ethics committee has approved the project, the provided appropriate channels record the Ethics Approval, together with all documents on which the approval is based.
8. For research where human subject data are collected, the researcher uploads an informed consent letter, to be reviewed by the ethics committee, in consultation with the data steward(s).
 - a. When the ethics committee has approved the informed consent letter, the appropriate channels record the informed consent letter.
9. The researcher can preregister the research protocol and data analysis plan (or grant proposal).
10. The appropriate channels should record all necessary information in a Data Processing Register, as required by the GDPR.
11. If the appropriate channels show that all required study preparation steps have been taken, the researcher can proceed with data collection.

Stage 2: Data Collection

Core Questions

- Are there instructions on security measures for data collection, and/or services and tools for data collection?
- Do adequate tools and services exist that comply with the principles of digital sovereignty?
- Are there sufficient security measures in place for the different types of research?
- Are these security measures clear for the researcher?

Steps

1. The researcher starts data collection.
2. The way in which the researcher handles the data responsibly depends on the type of research and the type of data.
3. When data collection has finished, or when a substantial part of the data collection has finished (e.g., a wave in a longitudinal study), the data are brought together in the workspace storage for further data processing (Stage 3).
4. Before data processing, it is recommended that the original raw data are submitted to a closed and secured “archive” (see Stage 4).

Stage 3: Data Processing

Core Questions

- What workspace storage solutions are offered by the institution?
- Do these workspaces comply with the principles of digital sovereignty?
- Are there instructions on how to handle data in the workspace storage?
- Are there instructions on how to collaborate with other researchers in the workspace?

Steps

1. The researcher can process the original raw data in a safe place that is designated for “workspace storage” (e.g., cloud storage, local storage, etc.).
2. If data are stored elsewhere (e.g., Qualtrics, other survey tools, cameras, etc.), the researcher needs to make sure the data are moved to one of the workspace options and thereafter deleted from the original storage facility.
3. If the data have been downloaded on a laptop, the researcher needs to make sure to also empty the “downloads folder” after the data have been properly stored in the workspace.
4. The researcher needs to make sure that a copy exists of the original raw data, before starting with the data processing.
 - a. For example, the researcher prepares a data package for archiving that includes the original unprocessed data file, a data description, and a code book. After archiving, the researcher removes the original (identifiable) data from the workspace and continues to work with the de-identified data.
5. If personal data are involved, the researcher should take measures to de-identify the data (i.e., work with anonymized data if possible; if anonymization is not possible: pseudonymize data; if pseudonymization is not possible: work with encryption).
 - a. The researcher sometimes needs to share (preferably de-identified) data with colleagues. *Research data should never be sent by e-mail!*
6. The researcher may only share (personal) data from subjects that have given their consent for sharing with external parties.
7. The researcher analyses the data to answer research questions.

Stage 4: Data Archiving

Core Questions

- Are there clear archiving guidelines in place (what, why, how, and when)?
- Is there the right support (both digitally as well as staff) in place for researchers to adhere to these guidelines?

Steps

1. The researcher notifies the data steward that a data package for archiving is ready (through the appropriate channels).
2. Multiple data packages for archiving can be submitted (e.g., once directly after data collecting, and again after a manuscript is completed).
3. The data steward does quality control (e.g., is it complete, does it comply with the FAIR requirements, and with other regulations (GDPR, purpose limitations, etc.)).
4. Hereafter the data package for archiving will be archived in a secured and closed archive that is only accessible by the dean.

5. Non-digital data (e.g., paper and pencil questionnaires, paper versions of informed consent forms) should also be archived. Digital informed consents should be archived in a separate folder.

Stage 5: Data Publication

Core Questions

- Are there clear publication guidelines in place (what, why, how)?
- Is there the right support (both digitally as well as staff) in place for researchers to adhere to these guidelines?

Steps

1. The researcher decides to publish (a part of) the research (meta)data.
2. The researcher makes sure that these data do not contain personal information. Preferably data should be anonymous, however, sometimes data cannot be completely anonymized. If the latter is the case, researchers should only publish the data after consultation with the data steward and under a restricted license.
3. The researcher needs to consider if an embargo on the publication of the data is needed (e.g., data will not be accessible during a certain period for reasons such as respondent safety, privacy, intellectual property, or commercial interests).
4. To ensure long-term usability, accessibility and preservation of data, the researcher must make use of a 'preferred' file format, preferably machine readable.
5. It is recommended that the researcher makes a data package for publication that includes the (meta)data file(s) to be published, a data description, the metadata, and a codebook. This data package can also be archived in the closed institutional archive.

Stage 6: Closing of the Research Project

Core Questions

- Is it clear for a researcher what to do when a research project is finished?
- Is there the right support (both digitally as well as staff) in place to be able to correctly close a project?

Steps

1. When the (final) data package for archival has been submitted by the researcher, the research project will be closed.
 - a. The data package for archival should contain the final files, such as the published manuscript.
 - b. The data steward checks whether the provenance is complete, and lastly archives the final data package in the secured archive.
2. The researcher (if possible) deletes all data from the workspace storage (all locations where data are stored) and dissolves the workspace storage folder.
3. If the researcher, or any collaborators, leaves the university and wants to take data with him or her, a data transfer agreement needs to be drafted. The data steward and legal affairs can help with such an agreement.
 - a. This has to do with ownership of the data, which does not exist. The university bears the responsibility over the data, which is transferred to the researcher after signing such a transfer agreement.

Appendix 4. Examples of data sharing decision trees

Case 1: An external researcher wants to gain access to a restricted data set (privacy-sensitive data)

Key Stakeholders: Primary Researcher, Department head, Privacy officers/ Privacy lawyers, Data Stewards, Data Subjects, Ethics Committee, University/ Institution, Functional managers

Key Factors: Cost, Location (inside or outside the European Economic Area), Data Sensitivity, University data policy, commercial funding, NDA

Decisions: Department Head (in practice done by researcher and data steward)

Use Case 2: Request for research data after employment has ceased, in collaboration with third parties (NDA)

Key Stakeholders: Primary Researcher, Department head, third party (pharmaceutical company)

Key Factors: Cost, Location (inside or outside the European Economic Area), Data Sensitivity, University data policy, commercial funding, NDA (Non Disclosure Agreement)

Decision: Third party legal department, Department Head

Case 3: The 10 year retention period is over and a decision must be made as to what will happen to the dataset. The cost of the 10 year archive period was covered by the institution but anything further is not.

Key Stakeholders: Primary Researcher, Department head, Privacy officers, Data Stewards, Data Subjects, Ethics Committee, University/Institution, Functional managers of the relevant data infrastructure

Key Factors: Cost, Location (EEA) European Economic Area, Data Sensitivity, University data policy, commercial funding, NDA

Decision: Department Head, Functional manager of the relevant data infrastructure

Appendix 5. Description of initiatives to support sharing sensitive research data

Project name	Brief content	Purpose
Personal health train	By setting up comparable data environments in different places, the same analysis model can be used on datasets at different institutions, and the results can be aggregated.	Apply Federated learning to different highly sensitive datasets, which remain in their own environment
Data exchange	Demonstrator of algorithm-to-data concept	Maintaining control over use of highly sensitive data, by reviewing the purpose of the study beforehand and the analysis and results afterwards
Secure Analyses Environment (SANE)	Solution for social sciences and humanities research in a research cloud environment to analyze data without giving access to the data	Enable the re-use of highly sensitive data that may not be accessed by other researchers or relocated
Research Data Exchange (RDX)	With RICDE ¹⁸ it creates a link between a data repository and a data analysis environment, where the conditions and contracts for reuse of data are regulated.	Provide opportunities for researchers to publish confidential data under enforced conditions
POC secure data archive	Proof of concept with an extra secure data archive on the SURF tape environment	Gain end-user experience with a secure environment

¹⁸ WRICDE = UvA Research Institute for Child Development and Education